

The Benefits of Agroforestry in Pig Farming

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Pigs eating mulberry leaves at Mas del Fray

Pig grazing in woodlands (silvopastoralism) or on wooded meadows is a traditional practice still widely used in Occitanie. Since pigs are very sensitive to heat, this practice is particularly beneficial in the south of France, where summers are hot. The Baron des Cévennes sector promotes this tradition and guarantees consumers a sustainable, high-quality product. It follows a strict set of specifications, which include the outdoor rearing of the pigs in oak and chestnut groves.

On the Mas del Fray farm in the Gard, Audrey Burban and Nicolas Villain practice outdoor pig farming in an agroforestry system on 5 hectares, mostly covered by oak and chestnut woodland. With the help of AGROOF, a consultancy specializing in agroforestry, they planted 70 trees in the non-wooded area between the fences and the electric wire, moving the wire one meter inward. For Audrey, electricity is the only effective way to protect young plants from the pigs.

The tree species were selected for pig farming (green oaks, white oaks, chestnut trees, mulberry trees, pear trees, and quince trees) to diversify the pigs' diet while providing them with shade. The mulberry tree is particularly interesting: it creates a large shade in summer, is very drought-resistant, withstands pollarding well, and pigs can eat its fruit and leaves. Its leaves are highly palatable, digestible, and nutritionally valuable (about 190 g of total nitrogen per kg of dry matter).

Pigs enjoy rubbing against the trees and can sometimes damage the bark of adult trees. To protect the existing trees, they use Cactus tree protectors supplied by AGROOF. Although quite expensive (€20 to €30 each), these protectors appear to be the most effective.

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Ver de Terre Production

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